

**THE IMPORTANCE OF SOLVING MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS
IN PRIMARY GRADES**

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Solving mathematical problems is an important component of teaching mathematics. It is unthinkable to master mathematics without solving problems. In mathematics, problem solving is an important way to put theory into practice. Problem solving plays an important role in the process of mastering one or another theoretical material studied in primary grades and develops students' thinking skills. Problems are created based on the system of practical cases. This means that the formation of each new concept is always done by solving some problem that requires its application, which helps to explain the significance of this concept.

Appropriate simple problems are used to reveal the content of arithmetic operations, connections between operations, components of operations and results, and connections between various quantities. Simple problems are necessary for students to solve complex problems. Problems are a useful tool for developing children's thinking skills and usually involve some knowledge. The search for this knowledge requires the problem solver to independently resort to analysis and synthesis, to compare facts, generalize, etc. Teaching these ways of knowing is one of the important goals of teaching mathematics.

When solving problems, interest in the subject develops, in general, independence, freedom, demandingness, hard work, and striving for the goal develop. Life issues also help to expand the circles of thought in the education of students. Working on problems systematically and on a planned basis leads to improvement of students' specific skills.

Work on the issue begins with mastering its content. At the beginning, when students do not yet have reading skills, it is necessary to learn to listen to the text of the problem read by the teacher, to distinguish the important elements of the condition aloud, then in order to better master the condition of the problem, each student it is necessary to listen to the text of the problem and read the problem independently. For this, it is necessary to offer them to read the problem first without making a sound, and then to read it expressively with a sound.

Studying problems in elementary grades is carried out with the help of forming new concepts, passing from solving simple problems to solving complex ones. In it, all kinds of simple problems of addition, subtraction, multiplication and division, that is, about finding the sum of the same addends, dividing by multiples and equal parts, increasing and decreasing the number several times problems on comparison of numbers, simple problems on finding unknown components of operations, as well as various complex problems, including problems solved by subtraction, problems on finding the sum of two multipliers and its inverse, then multiplying the sum, We will consider the following and other issues.

If the given problem is suitable or similar to the problems solved in the class with its complexity, then students should be taught to independently find the way to solve the proposed problem. For this purpose, students should acquire the simplest general methods of approaching problem solving.

Under the guidance of the teacher, students should be able to write down the condition of the problem in a short and clear way, and describe the condition with a drawing or a picture in order to facilitate finding ways to solve it. students should learn to clearly and clearly explain the results of the arithmetic operations, in what order they can find the answer to the problem. they should check the correctness of the solution.

Revealing the meaning of the actions of solving various types of problems, this or that concept, in addition to the formation of this or that relationship, serves to expand the scope of students' knowledge, to introduce them to some dimensions and the connections between them. In order for students to acquire the skills necessary for problem solving, it is necessary to teach them to understand and find certain connections between given and sought in different life situations. Thus, when working on solving problems, the student should not only think about one or the same problem, but should take care of the planned and systematic development of specific skills that form problem solving skills. Because the general complex skill of problem solving consists of these special skills.

References

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